

Supplementary information I

*Eumedlicottia burckhardti* (Böse, 1919)

1919 *Medlicottia burckhardti* (Böse); p. 18, pl. 1, Figs. 46–52, pl. 2, Figs. 1–3.

1940 *Medlicottia burckhardti* (Böse); (Miller and Furnish), pl. 3, Figs. 4–6, pl. 7, Fig. 1, pl. 8, Figs. 1–3, pl. 9, Figs. 1, 2, 4, pl. 10, Fig. 3.

1944 *Medlicottia burckhardti* (Böse); (Miller in King et al.), p. 84, Figs. 7a–b, pl. 22, Figs. 1–2, pl. 23, Figs. 3, 9.

1977 *Eumedlicottia burckhardti* (Böse); Nassichuk, p. 566, pl. 11, Fig. 8, text-fig. 3.

2000 *Eumedlicottia burckhardti* (Böse); Lambert et al., p. 163, pl. 8–3, Figs. 14, 15.

*Neogeoceras girtyi* (Miller and Furnish, 1940)

1940 *Medlicottia girtyi*; Miller and Furnish, p. 59, Fig. 14, 15A.

1944 *Medlicottia girtyi* (Miller and Furnish, 1940); Miller in King et al., 87, Fig. 7C, pl. 21, figs. 1, 2.

1965 *Neogeoceras girtyi* (Miller and Furnish, 1940); Nassichuk et al., p. 49, text-fig. 16A.

*Altudoceras* cf. *A. altudense* (Böse, 1919)

1919 *Gastrioceras altudense*; Böse, p. 88, pl. 3, Figs. 1–6.

1940 *Pseudogastrioceras altudense* (Böse); Miller and Furnish, p. 85, pl. 14, Figs. 1–6, pl. 17, Fig. 4, pl. 18, Figs. 1–7, pl. 19, Figs. 1, 4–6, pl. 20, Figs. 4, 5, pl. 21, Figs. 1, 2.

1944 *Pseudogastrioceras roadense* (Böse); Miller in King et al., p. 89, pl. 25, Figs. 1–4.

1961 *Pseudogastrioceras altudense* (Böse); Glenister and Furnish, text-fig. 13B.

1987 *Altudoceras* cf. *altudense* (Böse); Zhou, p. 326, pl. 5, Figs. 7–9.

1994 *Pseudogastrioceras roadense*; González-Arreola et al., p. 215–217, pl. 1, Figs. i, j, k.

2002 *Altudoceras altudense* (Böse); Leonova, p. 48.

2024 *Altudoceras* cf. *A. altudense* (Böse); Alanis-Pavón et al., p. 5–6, Fig. 3.5, Table 2.

*Strigogoniatites* cf. *S. kingi* Miller, 1944

1944 *Strigogoniatites kingi*; Miller, p. 92, text-fig. 9B, pl. 27, Figs. 1–3.

2002 *Strigogoniatites kingi* Miller; Leonova, p. 48.

*Roadoceras roadense* (Böse, 1919)

1919 *Gastrioceras roadense* Böse; p. 85, pl. 2, Figures. 28–47.

1940 *Pseudogastrioceras roadense* (Böse); Miller and Furnish, p. 89–91, pl. 15, Figures. 1–7, pl. 17, Figure. 5, pl. 18, Figures. 10, 11, pl. 28, Figures. 1–3.

1944 *Pseudogastrioceras roadense* (Böse); Miller, p. 89, Figure. 8, pl. 24, Figures. 2, 3, pl. 25, Figures. 1–6.

1946 *Pseudogastrioceras roadense* (Böse); Clifton, p. 558, pl. 85, Figures. 1, 2.

1994 *Pseudogastrioceras roadense* (Böse); González-Arreola et al., p. 215–217, pl. 1, Figures. i, j, k.

1985 *Roadoceras roadense* (Böse); Zhou, p. 196.

2002 *Roadoceras roadense* (Böse); Leonova, p. 48.

2024 *Roadoceras roadense* (Böse); Alanis-Pavón et al., p. 6, Fig. 3.6–3.11; 6.1–6.5; Fig. 7; Table 3.

*Neocrimites plummeri* (= *Metacrimites plummeri*) (Miller, 1944)

1944 *Adrianites plummeri* Miller; pl. 35, Figures. 1–2, Figure. 14B.

1950 *Neocrimites* (*Metacrimites*) *plummeri* (Miller); Ruzhencev, p. 202.

1997 *Millerites plummeri* (Miller); Cantu-Chapa, p. 66, Figure. 35C.

2002 *Metacrimites plummeri* (Miller); Leonova, p. 61.

*Pseudagathiceras difuntense* Miller, 1944

1944 *Pseudagathiceras difuntense* Miller; p. 101, text-figure. 15A, C, pl. 29, Figures. 6–12.

2002 *Pseudagathiceras difuntense* Miller; Leonova, p. 62.

*Pseudagathiceras spinosum* Miller, 1944

1944 *Pseudagathiceras spinosum* Miller; p. 103, text-figure. 15D, pl. 29, Figures. 1–5.

2002 *Pseudagathiceras spinosum* Miller; Leonova, p. 62.

*Stacheoceras gemmellaroi* Miller, 1944

1944 *Stacheoceras gemmellaroi* Miller; p. 107, pl. 37, Figures. 6–9, Figure. 18.

1977 *Stacheoceras gemmellaroi* Miller; Nassichuk, p. 576, pl. 2, Figures. 6, 7, 10, pl. 3, Fig. 6, text-figures. 10–12B.

1994 *Stacheoceras toumanskyae* Miller; González-Arreola et al., p. 215–217, pl. 1, Figures. f, g, l.

1997 *Stacheoceras gemmellaroi* Miller; Cantú-Chapa, p. 72, Figure. 40B.

2002 *Stacheoceras gemmellaroi* Miller; Leonova, p. 84.

2018 *Stacheoceras gemmellaroi* Miller; Leonova, p. 241

2024 *Stacheoceras* cf. *S. gemmellaroi* Miller; Alanis-Pavón et al., p. 6–7, Figures. 6.6–6.9; Fig. 8.

*Demarezites quirozii* new species

- 1944 *Waagenoceras dieneri* Miller; p. 109, pl. 31, Figures. 1–3, Figures. 19 A, B.
- 1987 *Demarezites* (Miller); Glenister and Furnish, p. 995.
- 1994 *Demarezites* n. sp. (Miller); Spinosa and Nassichuk, p. 1037, Figures. 1, 4–7.
- 2000 *Demarezites* n. sp. (Miller); Lambert et al., p. 178, pl. 8-2, Figures. 1–3.
- 2005 *Demarezites* sp. (Miller); Ehiro and Misaki, p. 10, Figures. 4.3 a–b, Figure. 5.1.

*Mexioceras guadalupense* (Girty, 1908)

- 1908 *Waagenoceras cumminsi* var. *guadalupense* (Girty); p. 502, pl. 29 Figures. 23–26.
- 1940 *Waagenoceras guadalupense* (Girty); Miller and Furnish, p. 60, pl. 6, Figures. 1–15, pl. 25, Figures. 4–6, pl. 39, Figures. 7, 8, pl. 40, Figures. 1–7, pl. 41, Figures. 1–7, pl. 42, Figures. 1–6, pl. 43, Figures. 1–3, text-figures. 47A, 48B, 49A–B.
- 1943 *Waagenoceras guadalupense* (Girty); Miller and Unklesbay, pl. 5, Figure. 1.
- 1944 *Waagenoceras guadalupense guadalupense* (Girty); Miller, p. 109, pl. 31, Figures. 1–3, Figure. 19A–B.
- 1955 *Mexioceras* (Girty); Ruzhencev, p. 701.
- 1969 *Mexioceras guadalupense* (Girty); Davis et al., p. 110, pl. 5, Figures. 4, 5.
- 1996 *Mexioceras guadalupense guadalupense* (Girty); Davis et al., p. 466, Figure. 1 F–G.
- 2005? *Mexioceras* sp. (Girty); Tasawa et al., p. 22, Figures. 4, 5E.
- 2009 *Mexioceras guadalupense* (Girty); Furnish et al., p. 153.

*Mexioceras smithi* (Miller and Furnish, 1940)

- 1940 *Waagenoceras guadalupense smithi* Miller and Furnish; p. 160, pl. 39, Figures. 7, 8, text-figures. 47B, 49C.

1944 *Waagenoceras guadalupense smithi* (Miller and Furnish); Miller, p. 109, pl. 32, Figures. 9–12, Figure. 19 C, D.

1955 *Mexioceras* (Miller and Furnish); Ruzhencev, p. 701.

1997 *Mexioceras guadalupense smithi* (Miller and Furnish); Cantu-Chapa, p. 88.

*Waagenoceras dieneri* Böse, 1919

1919 *Waagenoceras dieneri* Böse; p. 171, pl. 10, Figures. 18–31, pl. 11, Figures 1–27.

1940 *Waagenoceras dieneri dieneri* Böse; Miller and Furnish, p. 170, pl. 39, Figures 1–6, pl. 43, Figures. 4–7, pl. 44, Figure. 3. text-figures. 47D, 48A, 53B.

1944 *Waagenoceras dieneri* Böse; Miller, p. 111, 112, 114, pl. 25, Figure 7, pl. 31, Figures. 6–12, pl. 32, Figures. 1–8, pl. 33, Figures. 1–7, pl. 34, Figures. 1–9, Figures 21–23.

1977 *Waagenoceras dieneri* Böse; Nassichuk, p. 580, pl. 3, Figures. 3, 9–11, text-figures 12A, 15, 16.

1994 *Waagenoceras dieneri* Böse; González-Arreola et al., p. 216–217, pl. 1, Figure h.

2010 *Waagenoceras dieneri* Böse; Leonova, p. 273.

2024 *Waagenoceras* cf. *W. dieneri* Böse; Alanis-Pavón et al., p.8, Figures 6.10, 9.

*Waagenoceras girtyi* Miller and Furnish, 1940

1940 *Waagenoceras dieneri girtyi* Miller and Furnish; p. 158, pl. 6, Figures 35–39, text-figures 46, 47C, 53A.

1943 *Waagenoceras dieneri* Miller and Furnish; Miller and Unklesbay, p. 17, pl. 5, Figure 2.

1944 *Waagenoceras dieneri girtyi* Miller and Furnish; Miller, p. 112, pl. 25, Figure 7, pl. 31, Figures 6, 7, pl. 32, Figures 4–8, pl. 33, Figures 1–7, pl. 34, Figures 1–9, text-figures 21A, B, 22A, C, D, 23.

1972 *Waagenoceras girtyi* Miller and Furnish; Waterhouse, p. 253.

1977 *Waagenoceras girtyi* Miller and Furnish; Nassichuk, p. 581, pl. 3, Figures 7, 8, text-figures 17, 18.

2002 *Waagenoceras girtyi* Miller and Furnish; Leonova, p. 87.

*Waagenoceras karpinskyi* Miller, 1944

1944 *Waagenoceras dieneri karpinskyi* Miller; p. 112, pl. 31, Figures 8–12, pl. 32, Figures 1–3, text-figure 22B.

2002 *Waagenoceras karpinskyi* Miller; Leonova, p. 87.

*Timorites schucherti* Miller and Furnish, 1940

1940 *Timorites schucherti* Miller and Furnish; p. 175, text-figures. 57–59.

1944 *Timorites schucherti* Miller and Furnish; Miller, p. 115, pl. 35, Figures. 8–11, pl. 36, Figs. 1, 2, text-figures. 25, 26.

1997 *Coahuiloceras* Miller and Furnish; Cantú-Chapa, p. 82.

2002 *Timorites schucherti* Miller and Furnish; Leonova, p. 87.

*Paraceltites elegans* Girty, 1908

1908 *Paraceltites elegans* Girty; p. 499, pl. 25, Figures 12–14.

1919 *Paraceltites* aff. *elegans* Girty; Böse, p. 110, pl. 5, Figure 33–38.

1919 *Paralecanites altudensis* Girty; Böse, p. 18, 35, 178, pl. 11, Figures 20–45.

1940 *Paraceltites altudensis* Girty; Miller and Furnish, p. 70, pl. 23, Figures 1–3, pl. 24, Figure 7.

1940 *Paraceltites elegans* Girty; Miller and Furnish, p. 67, pl. 22, Figures 1–10.

1944 *Paraceltites altudensis* Girty; Miller, p. 123, pl. 41, Figures 1–6.

1944 *Paraceltites ornatus* Girty; Miller, p. 121, pl. 24, Figures 4–6, text-figure 29A.

1975 *Paraceltites elegans* Girty; Spinosa et al., p. 249, pl. 1, 2, Figures 1–7, pl. 3, Figures 1–9, text-figures 3, 4, 5C, 7, 10A–12.

1994 *Paraceltites elegans* Girty; González-Arreola et al., p. 216, 217, pl. 1, Figs. c–e.

2005 *Paraceltites elegans* Girty; Ehiro and Misaki, p. 11, Figures 6.8–9.

2024 *Paraceltites elegans* Girty; Alanis-Pavón et al., p. 8, Figures 6.11–6.13, 10.

*Cibolites* cf. *C. uddeni* Plummer and Scott, 1937

1937 *Cibolites uddeni* Plummer and Scott; p. 373, pl. 37, Figures 14, 15, text-figure 79.

1940 *Cibolites uddeni* Plummer and Scott; Miller and Furnish, p. 72, pl. 6, Figures 1–4, pl. 25, Figs. 7, 8.

1944 *Cibolites mojsisovicsi* Plummer and Scott; Miller, p. 124, pl. 42, Figure 1–5, text-figure 29C.

1975 *Cibolites uddeni* Plummer and Scott; Spinosa et al., p. 264, pl. 6, Fig. 1, text-figure 13.

2005 *Cibolites* cf. *C. uddeni* Plummer and Scott; Ehiro and Misaki, p. 12, Figures 8.2–8.4, 9.1, 9.2.